

Learning Assessment in a "Theses Debate"

Rosane Aragón¹, Crediné Silva de Menezes¹, Alberto Nogueira de Castro Júnior²

¹ Doctoral Program in Informatics Applied to Education, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre - RS, Brazil

² Institute of Computing, Federal University of Amazonas, Manaus – AM, Brazil

Email: rosane.aragon@gmail.com, credine@gmail.com, alberto@icompu.ufam.edu.br

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Abstract

In this scenario of constant expansion of digital information technologies, education saw significant opportunities to review its transmissive practices, generally limited by physical spaces that restrict communications and by the preponderance of analogic pedagogical resources. As an alternative to the use of this new scenario, we conceive a theoretical-methodological framework for the proposition of new active methodologies, which we call Pedagogical Architectures. We define them as structuring supports for learning, performed from the confluence of different components: strategy constructivist, digital technology (software, internet, artificial intelligence, and others), and flexible design of time and space. Although we can practice constructivism, at different levels of teaching, without the use of digital communication technologies, the introduction of these opens new learning possibilities, facilitating the interaction of students with the environment, with the objects of study, with their peers, and teachers. In addition, it favors the resignification of the notions of time and space. With the internet, we interact with objects and people, synchronously or asynchronously, geographically distributed, on a planetary scale. In this study, we experimented with the Pedagogical Architecture Theses Debate. We carried out the study, with 22 students of a doctoral program in Informatics in Education, in a Brazilian public university. We aimed to promote the knowledge construction cooperatively, with the support of a collection of testimonies on the topic Applications of information technology in education. Based on the students' prior knowledge, we held a collective debate in small groups, organized in successive stages of deepening and resignification. We realized the evaluation of learning through the analysis of the textual productions of the individuals, considering different stages of the debate, based on a list of categories created for this purpose. The results showed that the architecture reached its objective, supporting the reconstruction of knowledge.

Keywords: Active Learning; Pedagogical Architectures; Educational Technologies

1 Introduction

Use of active methodologies in the learning process emerged on the international scene in the first half of the 20th century, based on different theoretical contributions, including the works of Dewey (1930), Piaget (1953, 1971) and Vygotsky (1978). Some important elements are present in these contributions, of which we highlight: a) the subject does not acquire knowledge from a passive reception of the information presented to him, it is necessary to build new mental structures from the interaction with the world; b) social interaction is important to share different perceptions with other subjects and, c) It is not enough to know the world as it is at the moment, it is necessary to develop our intellect to produce innovations.

Regarding this last element, let's see what Jean Piaget says.

[...] The invention proper to the experimental spirit and to deduction only becomes rational if it is regulated thanks to the norms of objectivity and logical coherence, and these norms only take on a living value if they are applied to a constructive activity. [...] Piaget (1998)

The theoretical contributions presented above deal with the process of knowledge construction by individuals. However, to migrate from transmissive teaching to a constructivist practice, we still need to develop adequate pedagogical approaches. For the elaboration of constructivist proposals, we need to think about new pedagogical resources, new ways of organizing the school space, and the availability of technological solutions to favor interactions.

The organization of the school space is still restricted to physical spaces between four walls. However, the use of personal digital equipment has become part of the school scenario, giving opportunity to student production, using different media shared from geographically distributed workstations. Notably, in the context

of COVID-19 pandemic, school activities were carried out remotely, in all places where Internet access was available. However, this was not the reality of many developing countries.

Design and production of tangible teaching materials is too expensive both for the cost of production and for obsolescence, which has been attenuated using digital resources, allowing teachers to adopt different media instead of more conventional and expensive ones. In addition, cooperative development of resources, including methodologies, by a network of teachers and other professionals has also been carried out in an international movement led by UNESCO (Elder, 2019).

However, there is an obstacle to be overcome for these new materials meet the principles of active learning: a methodological basis. Our research group has been working in this direction and, in recent years, we have developed a framework to support the design of new proposals for active methodologies, which we call Pedagogical Architectures (Menezes and Aragón, 2018). In this article we present an experiment supported by an active methodology called "Theses Debate", built within this Framework. The results indicate that this proposal can contribute to the construction of knowledge in an active and cooperative approach.

2 Pedagogical Architectures

According to genetic epistemology (Piaget, 1971), learning results from the restructuring of a subject's network of meanings based on a process of rebalancing. In this sense, it is necessary for the subject to enter into cognitive conflict, which can be understood as an impossibility of explaining a fact of reality with his current knowledge. Rebalancing is then sought using the metacognitive operations of assimilation and accommodation. Conflicts can occur from the subject's interactions with the objects of the field of study, whether physical or conceptual, or through social interaction, which can be understood as a mediation process. Mediation can be carried out through interaction between students, called distributed mediation, or with the participation of teachers (Aragón, 2016). In view of our intention to make use of digital technologies, notably communication networks and artificial intelligence, the framework we propose already considers the possibilities of communication and mediation made possible by these two elements.

In line with these principles, we define a Pedagogical Architecture as a methodological framework articulated by the following components: the domain of knowledge; educational goals; students' prior knowledge of a certain domain; the problem-oriented interactionist dynamics; distributed pedagogical mediations; procedural and cooperative assessment of learning and support of digital technology (Menezes, Castro and Aragón, 2020).

2.1 Theses Debate

The practice of debate constitutes a socialization process that serves the development of citizenship and thinking (Parrat-Dayán, 2007). To support this process in education, one of the alternatives is to act in the perspective of promoting the exchange of points of view, which calls on students to position themselves in relation to others, but, at the same time, remain open to others views. The Theses Debate architecture is part of this perspective, constituting itself as a structuring framework for the construction of knowledge.

In this activity, the construction of knowledge is triggered by a set of statements, raised with the students and/or collected from the paradigmatic literature. From that point on, we can ask the participants to take a stand, whether they agree or not, followed by an argumentative justification. Subsequently, the arguers assume the role of reviewers and each one must analyse the arguments of one or more of their peers. This review does not seek to oppose the participants' conceptions, but to present problematizations so that each one can express their position more clearly. Once the reviews are completed, the participants return to their arguments and present replies to their reviewers, responding to the problems received and providing clarifications on points raised by the reviewers. Now, based on the reviews received from their reviewers, on the arguments and replies of their reviewers, each participant is invited to review their position and rewrite their arguments.

Figure 1. Development Flux in Theses Debate

3 The experiment

We have continuously used the Theses Debate pedagogical architecture in different disciplines, mainly in postgraduate (MSc/PhD) courses, in the training of professionals for the use of digital technologies in education. The experiment we present in this article deals with the application of this educational technology during the first semester of 2020, in the context of the Subject "Cooperative Learning in Digital Context". The choice was made because it was an edition with a greater number of students, which provides a greater diversity of situations and because it is the first opportunity to use it during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Twenty-two students (15 women and 7 men) from a doctoral program in Informatics applied to Education participated in that edition. The domain profile of the participants was: Education (5), Science Teaching (3), Mathematics Teaching (2), Computing (4), Communication (1), Administration (1), Arts (2) and Educational Technologies (4).

The discipline's principle is the development of its themes from active methodologies. Thus, to present the Theses debate Architecture, discuss its foundations and analyse its contributions to the learning process, we started with a debate on three theses covering "the use of digital technologies in education". Three theses were selected by participants from a list previously prepared by the teacher based on topics considered relevant in the context of the use of digital technologies in educational activities, according to the list presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Theses used in the experiment

<p>Thesis 1: Working in a collaborative environment is not the same of standardizing speech or thinking, but rather to bring together points of view in favor of everyone.</p> <p>Thesis 2: Using the internet, students can share results obtained in a problem to their colleagues, in a process that shortens the resolution of the work.</p> <p>Thesis 3: Digital games are addictive and distract students from learning; however, building games mixed with math challenges can increase students' interest.</p>

In agreement with the students, a schedule was prepared and provided 3 days for the first stage (position and initial argumentation) and 1 day for each of the four subsequent stages.

The computational support used was based on individual debate pages, one per participant, available on an online site, where participants had online access. Each column on the page should only be edited in the time interval defined in the schedule by the participants involved in the page.

Argumentator:							
Reviewer 1:							
Reviewer 2:							
Thesis	Stage 1		Stage 2		Stage 3	Stage 4	
	Initial positioning	Initial Argument	Review		Reply	Final positioning	Final Argument
Working in a collaborative environment is not synonymous with standardizing speech or thinking but bringing together points of view in favor of everyone.			R1				
			R2				
Using the internet, students can pass the results obtained in a problem to their colleagues, in a process that shortens the resolution of the work.			R1				
			R2				
Digital games are addictive and distract students from learning; however, building games mixed with math challenges can increase students' interest.			R1				
			R2				

Figure 2: Digital Debate Sheet

4 Argument Analysis

The analysis was carried out using a qualitative approach and focused on understanding the potential of the Theses debate Pedagogical Architecture (AP) to promote cooperative learning.

The data collection allowed us to propose and proceed with the categorization of the arguments developed by the 22 students, for each of the three theses, as well as observing the changes between the initial arguments (step 1) and the arguments elaborated after the stages of review and reply.

To carry out the analysis of the arguments, we defined 10 categories based on the justifications of the students' positions in relation to the three theses in the initial stage (categories C1 to C4) and in the final stage (categories C5 to C10) of the Pedagogical Architecture. The categories are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Categories of arguments

Initial Arguments
C1-Badly developed initial arguments, based on opinions and/or personal experiences (or that only repeat the thesis);
C2- Arguments developed based on interpretations of concrete evidence;
C3- Arguments based on theoretical/methodological contributions that support them;
C4- Arguments that bring contradiction with the positioning.
Final Arguments
C5- Arguments that repeat the initial ideas, without enrichment;
C6- Arguments that consider the ideas expressed by the reviewers and bring enrichment;
C7-Arguments enriched with new elements, regardless of the ideas expressed by the reviewers;
C8-Arguments that support new positions considering the ideas expressed by the reviewers;
C9- Arguments that support new positions regardless of the ideas expressed by the reviewers;
C10- Arguments that bring contradiction with respect to the positioning.

The categorization of the arguments, considering the categories in Table 2, allowed the elaboration of Table 3, which aims to present an overview of the arguments expressed by the subjects, considering each of the three theses, in the different stages of the cooperative work "Thesis Debate".

Table 3: Argument distribution by student category

Students	Initial argument (categories C1-C4)			Final arguments (Categories C5-C10)		
	Thesis 1	Thesis 2	Thesis 3	Thesis 1	Thesis 2	Thesis 3
S01	C1	C1	C1	C6	C6	C8
S02	C1	C1	C2	C6	C6	C5
S03	C3	C2	C3	C6	C6	C6
S04	C1	C1	C1	C8	C8	C8
S05	C1	C1	C1	C10	C6	C6
S06	C2	C2	C2	C5	C5	C5
S07	C2	C2	C1	C6	C8	C7
SC8	C2	C2	C3	C7	C6	C5
S09	C1	C4	C1	C6	C8	C9
S10	C2	C1	C2	C6	C6	C5
S11	C1	C1	C1	C8	C6	C8
S12	C4	C1	C2	C5	C5	C6
S13	C3	C2	C2	C6	C6	C6
S14	C3	C2	C2	C6	C6	C8
S15	C2	C2	C2	C6	C6	C6
S16	C2	C1	C1	C6	C6	C5
S17	C1	C2	C1	C6	C6	C8
S18	C1	C1	C1	C6	C6	C6
S19	C1	C1	C3	C6	C6	C7
S20	C1	C1	C1	C6	C6	C6
S21	C2	C3	C2	C5	C8	C6
S22	C1	C1	C2	C6	C6	C6

Based on Table 3, we prepared Tables 4 and 5, which allow us to observe the distribution of arguments by categories, considering the three theses (Thesis 1, Thesis 2, and Thesis 3) adopted for the development of Pedagogical Architecture. In each of the stages, 22 students argued justifying their positions in front of the theses, resulting in a total of 66 categorized arguments in each of the stages.

Table 4: Category distribution of arguments by thesis (initial stage)

Initial arguments	Thesis 1	Thesis 2	Thesis 3	Totals
C1-Badly developed initial arguments, based on opinions and/or personal experiences (or that only repeat the thesis);	11	12	10	33
C2- Arguments developed based on interpretations of concrete evidence;	7	8	9	24
C3- Arguments based on theoretical/methodological contributions that support them;	3	1	3	7
C4- Arguments that bring contradiction with the positioning.	1	1	0	2

Looking at Tables 4 and 5, we can say that most students (15 of the 22 students) started the AP, using poorly developed arguments, based on opinions and/or personal experiences or that only repeated the thesis. In this category (C1) it is possible to classify 33 justifications of positions, in at least one of the theses, by 15 students (6 students argued this way for the three theses, 6 students for 2 theses and 3 students for 1 thesis).

Arguments based on interpretations of concrete evidence (C2) were used to justify the positions of 16 students in 24 theses (2 students used this argument for 3 theses, 6 used it for 2 theses and 6 for 1 thesis). The arguments based on theoretical-methodological contributions (C3) were used by 7 students to justify their positions in 7 theses (6 subjects used this form of argument, none of them used to justify their position in all theses and only 1 student used argumentation to justify 2 theses).

Table 5 presents the distribution of the number of arguments per thesis.

Table 5: Category distribution of arguments by thesis (final stage)

Final arguments	Thesis 1	Thesis 2	Thesis 3	Totals
C5- Arguments that repeat the initial ideas, without enrichment;	3	2	5	10
C6- Arguments that consider the reviewers' ideas and bring enrichment;	15	16	9	40
C7- Arguments that are enriched with new elements, regardless of the ideas expressed by the reviewers;	1	0	2	03
C8- New arguments that support new positions, consider the reviewers' ideas;	2	4	5	11
C9- Arguments support new positions, regardless of the ideas raised by the reviewers.	0	0	1	01
C10-Arguments that bring contradiction with the positioning.	1	0	0	01

Regarding the students' arguments, in the final stage, we identified a prevalence of arguments that were enriched from the debate with the reviewers. In category C6, we identified 18 students who modified their arguments to support at least one of the three theses, totaling changes in the arguments of 40 of the 66 theses.

Changes in the arguments were identified, linked to a new position (agree, disagree, or partially agree), which were motivated by exchanges with reviewers who pointed out weaknesses in the initial argument and/or raised new arguments for the colleague, as well as their reflections from the contact with the arguments of colleagues.

Category C7 was identified in the arguments of 3 students. Each of the students modified their arguments in 1 of the 3 theses.

Of the 22 students, 7 subjects maintained their arguments in at least 1 of the 3 theses, that is, they repeated the initial arguments and positions (C5). Only one student finished the AP maintaining the same arguments for the three theses. This student, in the assessment space, expressed not having clearly understood the debate. Still, 1 student changed his position and arguments without the influence of exchanges with the reviewers (C9) and 1 student, in one of the theses, presented a contradictory position with his own arguments (C10).

5 Discussion and Final Remarks

The first result to be emphasized refers to the potential of Theses Debate to promote active and collaborative learning, considering the changes in the arguments related to the enhancement of ideas and changes in positions regarding the theses debated.

The experiment allowed us to observe qualitative changes in the arguments (due to the need to express them) and the advances in the understanding of colleagues' ideas and study on the theses under debate. These changes were predominantly due to improvement of initial arguments, even when there was no change in the position (agreement, disagreement, and partial agreement). In addition to those improvements, which were more frequent, changes in positioning were also identified, with the elaboration of new arguments, predominantly motivated by interactions with the reviewers, but also because of reflections after the first positioning. In all these cases, advances in the consistency of the arguments were evidenced.

Positions and arguments about thesis 1 (20 of the 22 students in the final stage agreed) and thesis 2 (18 of the 22 students in the final stage) showed us that they consider cooperative work relevant for learning. They understand that cooperative learning is not reduced to an abbreviation of work, but to a construction that takes place through the coordination of different points of view.

Considering students' evaluations, we can say that the experience of collaborative work reinforced the importance of exchanges in active learning. The review stage proved to be relevant for the improvement of arguments, with advances both in consistency and expression of ideas as well as development of critical thinking.

Regarding the work dynamics and use of the virtual environment, the evaluations showed that it was positive, allowing more activity and protagonism from students. Most students considered that the environment was adequate to support the architecture, although three students found some initial difficulties in using it. Some students expressed that they perceived possibilities of using Theses Debate in their work contexts, with the necessary adjustments according to student age and pedagogical objectives. They mentioned, for example, the adoption of different theses for each subject and division into groups based on the positions favoring the discussion between those who agreed and those who disagreed.

Regarding criticisms and suggestions, most students expressed that they would have carried out interactions for longer so that they would become more familiar with work dynamics and would have more time for reflection. Some students suggested that, in future AP applications, more material should be made available before all stages; the introduction of a new specific stage for online discussions by the entire group; and further time to the establishment of connections supported by a theoretical framework. It was also suggested the use of a specific (custom-made) environment for Theses Debate.

As a result of the authors' findings and suggestions of the students, an updated version of a specific environment for Theses Debate is being produced, and will have new features to automate the organization of stages and facilitate teacher mediation. In addition, new stages like search for approximations and differences between arguments and formation of groups for the elaboration of argumentative texts are to be implemented. These improvements will be the subject of future work.

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